

ON THE ISSUE OF THE NEED FOR CHANGES IN THE FIELD OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE MODERN CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CAPITALISM

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***Abstract.** The essay emphasizes that in the current conditions of globalist chaos, changes in state formations are a small hope to create changes in education not only for most universities, but for a single university. Trends in modern education in the digital age play an important role in the development of not only national universities but also specific departments. In the conditions of modern globalist chaos of change of state formations we will address the question of what direction of development of higher technical education awaits us in the further development of capitalism. We can safely point out four main directions of capitalist neo-feudalization: parcelling, ie fragmentation with the simultaneous strengthening of sovereignty; new quasi-state hierarchy (exponential growth of inequality); geographical polarization between the metropolis and the hinterland; apocalyptic imaginary reality from which people are saved by drugs. All these tendencies show similar features in the European Middle Ages, but today they acquire completely different social and technological forms. At the global level in the knowledge and technology industry, revenues from intellectual property rents exceed revenues from production. The share of financial services in GDP exceeds the share of industrial goods. Less and less capital is re-invested in production,*

instead it accumulates in accounts, is spent or redistributed as rent. How effective can IT education be? Mass or elite education? What are the problems of training quality specialists in universities? What are the causes of gender inequality in education? How to restore confidence in technical education in Ukraine? Today, the topic of education worries many. A small minority has benefited from the progress of intellectual technology. Most were doomed to a senseless, robotic existence. Now anyone can buy a cheap device with which he can get any help and solve any problem of intermediate level of intelligence, which previously required long training and intelligence. You don't have to remember anything. There is nothing to think about. Everything is already thought out by professionals. You don't have to study and train your mind for years. The problem of whether it is possible to create artificial intelligence that transcends human intelligence has been solved for most people by their nonsense and stupidity. In our private opinion, the essay is deontological in nature, which, like the critique of practical reason, covers only part of the problems of higher education.

Keywords: *Higher Education; globalist capitalism; transport technologies; neo-feudalism; parcelling of sovereignty.*

The basis of the problem. In the conditions of the modern globalist chaos of changing state formations, let us turn to the question of what direction of development of higher technical education awaits us with the further development of capitalism. But first, let's look at the trends in the development of capitalism, and then move on to considering the future of specialized higher technical education in transport technologies.

Main content. Analyzing the immediate past, we can safely point to four main directions of capitalist's neo-feudalization: parceling, that is, fragmentation

with a simultaneous strengthening of sovereignty; new quasi-estate hierarchy (exponential growth of inequality); geographic polarization between the metropolis and the hinterland; an apocalyptic imaginary reality from which people are saved by drugs. All these tendencies reveal similar features in the European Middle Ages, but today they take completely different social and technological forms. Thus, communicative capitalism turns citizens into totally dependent on IT platforms, within which they are not free workers, but passive sources of data. If this hypothesis is correct, then palliative remedies for fighting injustice, such as democracy and free elections, will no longer work.

Globalist capitalism potentially tends towards neo-feudalism. This is indicated by signs that capitalism may turn into something worse: neo-feudalism of new lords and serfs, a micro-elite of platform billionaires, and a gigantic service or servant sector. Today, as the processes of real subordination (subsumption) of labor to capital turn against themselves, capitalism is turning into something worse. The monopoly concentration of modern communicative capitalism, rapidly growing inequality, the subordination of the state to the market lead to neo-feudalism, where accumulation is carried out not only through the production of goods, but also through services, rent, debt and power. For example, globally in the knowledge and technology industry, intellectual property rental income exceeds product revenue. The share of financial services in GDP exceeds the share of industrial goods. Less and less capital is re-invested in production, instead it accumulates in accounts, is spent or redistributed as rent. This means that value is less and less involved in the creation of new value, in self-valorization (Selfstverwertung). Valorization is the reproduction by capital of the conditions for the production of surplus value through social mechanisms. At the same time, self-valorization also refers to alternative mechanisms for the self-reproduction of the

labor force by the workers themselves, without capital. The processes of valorization - the build-up of fixed capital - have gone far beyond the limits of production and banks, penetrating into complex, speculative, unstable areas in which the role of close supervision, coercion and violence is growing more and more. Neo-feudalism is called something worse, what capitalism strives for and becomes. Neo-feudalism is what awaits us.

Trends do not completely determine the situation, but leave space for political action and the need for it. We ourselves are part of this situation. Capitalism is turning into something even worse. And yet we can intervene and prevent it.

By "capitalism" we mean a system in which private property, wage labor and commodity production underlie the accumulation of fixed capital. For its own reproduction and legitimization, the capitalist system needs a specific state form, a bourgeois legal state that claims justice and neutrality. Contemporary communicative capitalism is a system tending toward neo-feudalism as its own processes become more intense and turn against themselves.

But there is also another extreme form of social structure, which also leads to neo-feudalism. This is socialism. This is not a paradise on earth, but a political form in which the place of production in the interests of the accumulation of capital by a minority is replaced by production to satisfy the needs of the majority, a form of collective self-emancipation of the proletarianized masses. The concentration and monopolization of power, control levers and material resources in the hands of the socialist elite led to an extreme separation from the working masses and the emergence of a layer of social neo-feudal lords.

Similarly, the monopoly concentration of modern communicative capitalism, the rapidly growing inequality, the subordination of the state to the market lead to

neo-feudalism, where accumulation is carried out not only through the production of goods, but also through rent, debt and power.

Based on the above formulated theses, four complementary characteristics of neo-feudalism can be distinguished: 1) parceling of sovereignty; 2) hierarchy and expropriation with the participation of new lords and peasants; 3) abandoned hinterlands and privileged cities; 4) feeling of insecurity and catastrophism.

But what if we are no longer dealing with capitalism, but with something worse? In response, current trends can be outlined that indicate that capitalism may turn into something worse, a neo-feudalism of new lords and serfs, a micro-elite of platform billionaires, and a gigantic service or servant sector. The paradigm of education in the information age reflects the global trend of transformations that this sphere of human life is going through, and shows directions outside of state programs and together with them.

We live in an information society that has gone through many "iterations" since the industrial age, so it's very difficult to use educational recipes that were in place 150-200 years ago. And some countries have long understood this. How effective can IT education be? mass or elite?; problems of training high-quality specialists in universities, as well as the causes of gender inequality in the industry. How to restore confidence in technical education in Ukraine?

Today, the topic of education worries a lot of people. There are many informal initiatives concerning education, both at the local level and Internet initiatives that go far beyond the cities of the country. This is a long trend that will greatly affect the future world. It is obvious that already today people independently come to the conclusion that it is possible to change the country with the help of education. Because "naked" reforms alone are not enough for this."

It took very little time to notice one striking phenomenon. Despite all the external, gender, age, professional, service and other differences, something prevails in all students that makes them all the same. Same as ants. And it is better to say - like robots of the same series. What's the matter here? Two reasons for this have been identified.

We are dealing with virtually unlimited information about everything in the world. Whatever we do, after several months of “bathing” in the same ocean of information, we involuntarily accumulate in ourselves approximately the same amount of information and develop approximately the same ability to extract information. Our natural differences are leveled out due to the same intellectual information technology and the same awareness. This is the first of the reasons mentioned.

A small minority has benefited from the progress of intellectual technology. The majority turned out to be doomed to a meaningless, robotic existence. Now anyone is able to purchase a cheap device with which he can get any help and solve any problem of an average intellectual level, which previously required a lot of training and intelligence. Nothing needs to be remembered. You don't have to think about anything. Everything is already thought out by professionals. No need to study and train the mind for years. The problem of whether it is possible to create an artificial intelligence that surpasses the human one, for most people, was solved by making them stupid.

Intelligent technology has invaded areas where it is completely unnecessary. The vital problems in these areas are not mathematical or technical problems. Here we are talking about the different interests of the participants in some operations, about the struggle between them, about the balance of power. The ordinary human mind is more than sufficient here. The decisive role here is played by the desires

and will of counterparties, and not by finding some optimal options. The use of intellectual technology here creates the illusion of the importance of the mind, masks the banal essence of the matter and gives justification for dishonorable acts. Serious researchers have long established that in ninety cases out of a hundred, when the most complex intellectual technology is used, one can, in principle, do without it.

There are also numerous cases when it is the use of intellectual technology that is an obstacle to solving problems. So, on no computers and with no empirical data can you develop a scientific understanding of an event, physical or social phenomenon. What is needed here is not a computer mind, which is a hypertrophy of only individual properties of the human intellect, and the simplest ones at that, but a mind of a completely different type, a creative, wide, multifaceted, flexible, dialectical mind. Computer thinking has killed the living fabric of knowledge and creativity. A huge mass of stupidity, ignorance, obscurantism has been loaded into the artificial intelligence of mankind. In understanding our society, our life and ourselves, we found ourselves at the level of our primitive ancestors.

Computers have brought new diseases with them and have themselves become disease-prone. Computer medicine emerged and quickly reached a high level. It is divided into two branches. One of them studies and treats (or rather, tries to treat) human diseases that are specifically related to computers - human computer diseases. Now there are several hundred types of such diseases, for example, Eva Adams syndrome. This is the most common disease. Moreover, it is difficult to distinguish between the norm and the disease. Experts believe that in ninety cases out of a hundred, the norm is not respected and turns into a disease. Due to the advent of computer memory storages (they are called cemeteries of souls), Eve Adams syndrome has become a common disease in personal

computers. Frequent diseases are a special mania of omnipotence, omniscience, omniscience, genius - in the aggregate they give the God Complex. And such illnesses as lack of will, superpedantry, memory loss, loss of sense of time, primitivization of the intellect, etc., have become commonplace in the psyche of Westerners and are not even considered diseases. There are diseases that only special computer devices can diagnose.

The second branch of computer medicine studies and treats diseases of computers. These are not just technical breakdowns of computers - such breakdowns are not within the scope of medical attention. This is the essence of a malfunction in the operation of technically sound computers, similar to human diseases. The first diseases of this kind were disorders and destruction of computer intelligence due to the emergence or deliberate introduction of fragments of information into it, called viruses, since their effect on the information contained in computers and the program turned out to be similar to the effect of biological viruses on a living organism. At the end of the 20th century, the number of such "viruses" reached two thousand. Their appearance and spread caused alarm around the world, jeopardizing the entire computer sphere. Then came the carriers of computer diseases of other types, similar to biological ones. Disorders of computer systems similar to human mental illnesses have also appeared. They have not yet been studied. So far, there are no defenses against them. You just have to replace sick computers with new ones, which is extremely expensive.

Education trends in the digital age. Digital technologies help to choose an individual learning path for each student, increase objectivity in assessment and radically reduce the burden on teaching staff. To achieve these goals, it is planned to switch to the mass use of modern digital educational and methodological complexes. For students, these complexes will draw up individual programs, select

the best methods and formats for studying the material for each, and help professors fill out reports and journals, check essays, reports and abstracts, that is, they will free up his time for a creative approach. At the same time, simulators should be introduced into the educational process. This will make learning visual and help develop 21st century skills: teamwork, critical thinking and creativity. The development of distance and blended learning systems will allow you to study materials where and how convenient, and you come to the University for seminars and exams. So distance learning helps to master the material faster.

It is impossible to study in accordance with modern requirements if universities are not sufficiently equipped and there is no modern material and information infrastructure. What is the way to move forward? To begin with, all universities should be connected to the Internet at a speed of 1 Gb / s. This will allow you to watch videos in HD quality and provide the basis for the formation of a digital environment. The democratization of society provides equal opportunities for everyone. For all students, make available pre-training programs, it is possible to offer an educational certificate with a deferred payment of tuition fees. Provide targeted support to students from low-income families, including free additional classes and other additional education, participation in summer labor camps, and so on. For students with material resources below the subsistence minimum, introduce social scholarships of at least 80% of the regional subsistence minimum. These actions will equalize educational opportunities, which will allow many of those who in the current situation do not succeed to achieve personal and professional success. One of the interesting directions is new technological education. In view of the fact that universities do not have the necessary equipment, it is proposed to bring the education system into line with the real labor market. The system of technological education at universities should be radically updated. Equip them

with modern workshops and laboratories, build a system of student technoparks. To use the resources of universities to train students with the help of networked forms of education. Develop and introduce into wide practice digital simulators and simulators that will help master skills in priority qualifications. Most of the educational programs at universities should be transferred to prestigious applied bachelor's programs, and more often - to short programs (from 6 months) for obtaining professional qualifications in advanced training centers. As a result, we will get a large number of students with high-quality knowledge in the field of technological, computer and information literacy. This, accordingly, will inevitably lead to an increase in the "cost" of graduates of applied bachelor's programs in the labor market. The introduction of a system of continuous education will attract adults to participate in learning. This will positively affect not only labor productivity, but also the financial situation of people and their social well-being. Create retraining and advanced training programs for adults. To do this, use the models of distance learning and massive open online courses of universities, and after the employment assistance program. Working specialists could pay for training and an independent examination jointly with the state, while the training of the unemployed should be carried out entirely at the expense of the state. Organize a single national electronic platform-navigator of educational programs and employment services, including for pensioners.

In recent years, universities have acted as centers of innovation. World experience shows that it is universities that become the backbone of the technological and innovative development of regions and states. It is necessary to build a system for the development of entrepreneurial competencies among students, for which at least a third of educational programs in universities should be based on online courses from leading universities. Transfer to universities the

regional innovation support infrastructure: business incubators, business accelerators, innovation parks, technology parks. Support 100 universities on the basis of competitive selection for the development of the regional economy and 25 universities for the development of industries. Ensure the development of fundamental science in universities. Expand the programs of international competitiveness - on the basis of 50 universities, deploy experimental sites for large international projects of the Megascience level. And at least 50 centers of excellence - international research centers in various fields of science with the involvement of at least 10 thousand abroad ny researchers. To develop funding for long-term (from 5 to 10 years) programs of fundamental and exploratory research at leading research universities and research centers. Establish a modern infrastructure for teaching foreign students. Build new and upgrade existing campuses, build dormitories. In leading universities, increase the number of teachers with knowledge of English up to 90%. Facilitate immigration procedures.

Conclusion and prospects for further development. In our essay, we have tried to paint a picture of the current state, as well as the near future of higher education in the rapidly changing modern environment. Taking into account the above trends, it is necessary to dwell in more detail on the areas of development of the Department of Transport Systems and International Logistics. It seems reasonable to us to outline the following ways of development of the department, namely: to open a new specialty "Transport Logistics"; to join the international European program Erasmus + "Smart Transport and Urban Logistics" (SMA LOG), to provide opportunities for undergraduate students to study at European universities; expanding the participation of teachers in educational programs implemented in a foreign language, finding ways to develop and expand cooperation with the departments of the world's leading universities; ensuring a

stable enrollment of foreign students in the specialty; providing students with a wide range of additional educational services and opportunities to develop soft skills as a necessary component of successful professional self-realization and competitiveness.